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D5.1 Dissemination and exploitation strategy plan

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D5.1 Dissemination and exploitation strategy plan

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Abbreviations

DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
FP	Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development
H2020	Horizon 2020 EU Research and Innovation Program
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document establishes a dissemination and exploitation strategy plan for the INTEND project. It has been implemented by Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) / Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT) Team with the review from INTEND Work Package Leaders, and it will be used as a guide of the dissemination Plan and strategy for all INTEND team members.

This document provides an effective Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy Plan which has as main target to increase the visibility of the key project outputs and outcomes and link with key initiatives relevant for the project and the scope of implementation.

1 Introduction

The overall objective of the INTEND project is to deliver an elaborated study of the research needs and priorities in the transport sector utilising a systematic data collection method. One of the main elements of the INTEND project is the review of pertinent literature (EU and international research projects including strategic research agendas, studies or roadmaps) in order to identify future technologies for each transport mode (road, aviation, rail, maritime) as well as infrastructure and transport systems which will be treated horizontally. The INTEND project will also review past forward looking projects and relevant recent studies in order to present future mobility concepts. Megatrends that will be affecting the future transport system will be identified using literature review. To ensure validity of the results, the Analytical Network Process (ANP) will be used to weight the megatrends, the influence of technological development trends as well as the one of political imperatives and derive reliable outcomes on the most predominant trends. Finally, INTEND will develop a transport agenda that would pave the way to an innovative and competitive European Transport sector. The project is driven by three main objectives:

- Define the transport research landscape
- Define the Megatrends and their impact on research needs
- Identify the main transport research needs and priorities

To enable a wide range of stakeholders to gain access to the results, INTEND will also develop an online platform, the INTEND Synopsis tool that will constitute a dynamic knowledge base repository on the major developments in the transport sector. This will provide a visualisation of main outcomes resulting from the already described ANP. The basis for the platform will be Transport Synopsis Tool which is already developed under the project RACE2050 coordinated by TUB. The repository will be updated and integrated into the INTEND website to provide a comprehensive picture of all forward looking studies focusing on technological developments, megatrends and policies.

1.1 The INTEND work structure

Figure 1 depicts the work flow of the INTEND project and the relationship between dissemination, communication and exploitation activities of WP5 with the rest of the WPs.

WP5 leader, CERTH / HIT, is responsible for delivering the overall structure and processes to enable an effective communication and dissemination of all knowledge gathered during the project as well as the outputs it produces during its lifetime. In order to maximize the project's output, it is of essential importance that all project partners contribute to the implementation of an effective Communication and Dissemination strategy plan for the knowledge gathered during the project as well as the outputs it produces during its lifetime.

1.1.1 The deliverable in the frame of INTEND work structure

D 5.1 is one of the key deliverables of the INTEND project, as it describes and outlines all the key dissemination and exploitation activities in the strategy plan for the project. This strategy is crucial for maximising the impacts of the project. Effective dissemination of the project's results is of utmost importance in order to maximise the project impact and reach out to the public and EU officials who are the main target groups of the project. For the INTEND project, the foundation of this strategy will be based on a detailed understanding of the importance of forward looking strategies in transport planning and research agenda

development. This will help ensure that the right information, communicated in the most appropriate way, reaches the right people at the right time.

Figure 1. Workflow in INTEND and relations of WPs

To maximise the project's exploitation potential a Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) has been drafted in the framework of this deliverable. The INTEND Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP), will evolve throughout the course of the project. The very first step in the DCP has been the identification of the target audience. INTEND consortium has engaged a good sample of these target groups already in former initiatives and past projects including FUTRE, RAC2050, OPTIMISM, METRIC, INTRASME, MOBILITY4EU and there is already a database of more than 400 transport professionals (including policy makers, industry, public and private sector stakeholders and experts interested in the research agenda development).

1.1.2 Task 5.1: Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation

This task has been built on four (4) pillars which are: 1) Online presence, 2) Dissemination material, 3) Events and 4) Final event: reality check of the Research Agenda. For every pillar mentioned above, a short description is given below.

Online presence

INTEND website and social networking presence are the major project dissemination tools. From the existing social media the Project uses Facebook, Twitter and Linked-in. The website and the social networking pages will be reviewed and upgraded continuously with

content/news added throughout the project’s lifetime. The website will also offer a private area to facilitate information management within the consortium.

Dissemination material

A range of dissemination material (logo, brochures and flyers) will be produced by CERTH / HIT. Three e-newsletters will be sent (M4, M8, and M12) to registered website users as well as the networks (see Table 1 and Table 4) of each individual partner. In addition partners will be requested to keep track of the numbers of emailed newsletters sent to recipients and report these numbers to CERTH in order to update relevant metrics as described in section 5.10 (Reporting and Monitoring of dissemination activities). A more detailed reference regarding the dissemination material is included in the next sections.

Table 1: INTEND networks

	Policy makers	Industry	Public	Private
CUE	5	30	30	30
CERTH	13	21	22	3
FTTE	10	10	20	20
ZHAW	10	10	50	30
TUB	10	10	15	10

Events

All INTEND partners will represent the project in relevant conferences, international, European and national/local events (eg TRA, ICTTE, etc). These will not be just conferences but formal or informal meetings that could be carried out by other EU/national funded initiatives. The goal will be to create synergies and support the dissemination of the project results. A more detailed reference regarding the events will take place in section 5.6.

Final event

The final event is further explained in section 5.8.

1.1.3 Interrelations of Task 5.1 with other Tasks of the project

The interrelations between Task 5.1 and other Tasks of the project are depicted in Figure 2:

Figure 2. Interrelations of Task 5.1 with other Tasks of the project

Specifically, Task 5.1 receives feedback from the following Tasks:

Task 2.1 Review and assessment of pertinent literature

Task 2.2 Identification of key transport concepts of the future

Task 2.3 Political imperatives

Task 3.1 Megatrends identification

Task 3.2 Validation and impact assessment of Megatrends and Policies

Task 4.1 Sketch of the future transport system

Task 4.2 Gap Analysis

Task 4.3 Transport research agenda: blueprint on transport research needs, priorities and opportunities

Task 5.3 Web tools

2 Dissemination and communication target groups

WP5 will deliver the formal structure and processes to enable effective Communication and Dissemination of all knowledge gathered during the project as well as the outputs it produces during its lifetime. The ultimate aim of this WP is to increase the visibility of key project outputs and outcomes and link with key initiatives relevant to the project and the scope of implementation. More specifically the objectives of WP5 are to:

Task 5.1:

- Develop and update a Dissemination, Communication and exploitation plan
- Define relevant target groups and create and maintain a growing contacts database

D5.1 Dissemination and exploitation strategy plan

- Define and elaborate a set of key project messages and tailor messages for each of the various target groups
- Produce a wide range of online and printed dissemination material
- Devise an effective social media campaign, using mainly LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook

Task 5.2:

- Deliver a Data Management Plan (DMP) outlining how data will be managed effectively

Task 5.3:

- Develop a project website
- Using effective communication tools, ensure a broad awareness of project activities and results amongst key stakeholders identified in the Dissemination and Communication Plan
- Deliver a visual depiction of the results by developing: 1. Project database incorporated in INTEND's website and 2. Updated transport Synopsis Tool

The following paragraphs list the main target groups of the INTEND dissemination and communication strategy and their roles sorted by priority. The following groups will be formed based on partners' relevant contact lists as noted in section 1.1.2 and Table 4.

2.1 Private sector actors

Private sector actors comprise small and big private companies, interested in investing their production efforts towards the most promising technologies that address the future challenges. It also includes a range of relevant industrial groups and actors (such as UNIFE, CLEPA , etc)

2.2 Research and academia

Universities and research centres will be greatly benefit from INTEND results in directing their research efforts to address future challenges. From a methodological view point, INTEND offers an innovative combination of Megatrends identification based on qualitative data derived not only from pertinent literature but also from experts' knowledge based on the Analytical Network Process analysis, which may prove to be an interesting tool for further exploitation in futurology studies.

2.3 Transportation agencies and authorities

INTEND will provide concrete recommendations on research investment directions that would meet economic efficiency, competitiveness, sustainability, user convenience and inclusiveness objectives. Relevant stakeholders include, for example, the Transport for London, Nahverkehrsgesellschaft Baden-Württemberg (NVBW), Parma Municipality (Italy), South East Europe Transport Observatory (SEETO), Swiss cities authorities. Further, transport stakeholders that the INTEND consortium will approach can be found in section 5.

2.4 Policy makers and influencers

The ultimate goal of INTEND is to provide a research agenda that can be used for policy drafting. Relevant stakeholders include transport decision and policy makers as well as

regional, national, and European authorities linked to decision-making processes and funding agencies. The policy recommendations will be enabling informed decisions. In addition each partner will reach out to various national organisations and organisations that may influence transport /technology policy and decision making.

A target number of 100 such informal meetings is foreseen in the project based on the amount of stakeholders presented at Table 1. About 50 such meetings are expected to take place with relevant stakeholders that are regularly contacted by the project partners. In addition, at least another 50 meetings are anticipated to take place within the context of the events that will be attended by the partners as part of the secondary dissemination activities and other national and European level events.

3 INTEND visual identity

Under the guidance of CERTH / HIT, a professional graphic designer has developed a logo and visual identity templates comprising diverse dissemination materials (e.g. flyer, newsletter, PPT template) in accordance to the H2020 visual guidelines. This visual identity ensures high recognition value of INTEND throughout various communication channels.

The INTEND logo (Figure 3) consists of a graphic element and the project acronym. The graphic element refers to the modes of transport hence the different colours and arrow directions (land and rail together with green colour, air with deep blue colour, water with light blue). The cross-linkage between the lines depicts the interconnectivity and cooperation of these modes of transport.

Figure 3. INTEND logo

4 Communication material

In order to maximize the potential for the successful exploitation of INTEND and the uptake of the project's method and outcomes, the dissemination activities in DCP have been designed following a number of objectives and proposing a number of methods, which are summarized in the following table (Table 2):

Table 2. Overview of dissemination activities

OBJECTIVE	MEANS	TARGET GROUP	MEASURABLE INDICATORS (target value)
Raise the profile of INTEND	Multimedia Conference Presentations/attendance Posters, rolls-ups, Banners, Brochures Media Highlights	All Members of the public, attendees of the final conference and stakeholders	Presentations at Conferences (4); Number of viewers of project audiovisual material in YouTube (>1,000); Multimedia presentation (1); number of entries (articles, podcasts, interviews) in local-regional-national media (30); Project website visits (>9000)
Enhance the stakeholders understanding on INTEND	Project website	All	Number of visits to project website (>9000)
	Project Newsletter, social media campaign (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn)	General public Media Research Policy makers	Number of newsletters (3); number of newsletters recipients (1,000); number of aggregated "followers" (2,000); Article in Wikipedia (1); social media updated regularly
	Seminars, scientific papers, publications	Academia	Number of papers and publications (4)
	Press releases	All	Number of releases (2)
	Networking	All	Final event (50+ participants)
Drive action: support the dissemination & exploitation of the INTEND results	Presentations, articles, stands at fairs-events, contribution to platforms, networks and relevant organizations, follow up activities	Research Industry Policy Makers CSO/NGOs	Networking and participation in relevant events (10); Industry related events (4); number of local presentations (10), number of informal meetings with local private companies, public authorities,

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			policy makers (100)
Mainstreaming: feeding results and experiences into policy	Deliverables, presentations, meetings with relevant experts, specific policy papers/briefs	Policy Makers	Deliverables of project (11) meetings and gatherings with policy makers (4); policy recommendations (3) D4.1, D4.2, D4.3

To accomplish the dissemination activities targets, the partners will exploit meetings with the relevant stakeholders that they regularly consult with, by including an INTEND discussion item in the meeting agendas, as well as the meetings listed under secondary dissemination activities as noted under section 2.4 Table 6

A break down and allocation of the dissemination activities to each partner of the target set in Table 1 are presented at Table 3 below

Details on how to attain the quantitative targets are presented in section 5.10- Reporting and monitoring of dissemination activities. A relevant section with specific details on how the targets have been achieved will be included in the project final report.

Table 3. Allocation of targets per partner for dissemination activities

Partner	Indicator	Target
CUE	Presentations at Conferences	1
	Number of entries in local regional national media	6
	Newsletters recipients	200
	Social media followers	400
	Number of publications/papers	1
	Number of press releases (produced by CERTH, distributed to media by the partner)	1
	Networking and participation in relevant events	2
	Industry related events	1
	Local presentations	2
	Informal meetings with local private companies, public authorities, policy makers	20
	Meetings and gatherings with policy makers	1
CERTH	Presentations at Conferences	1
	Number of entries in local regional national media	6
	Newsletters recipients	200
	Social media followers	400
	Number of publications/papers	1
	Number of press releases (produced by CERTH, distributed to media by the partner)	1
	Networking and participation in relevant events	2
	Industry related events	1
	Local presentations	2
	Informal meetings with local private companies, public authorities, policy makers	20

	Meetings and gatherings with policy makers	1
FTTE	Presentations at Conferences	1
	Number of entries in local regional national media	6
	Newsletters recipients	200
	Social media followers	400
	Number of publications/papers	1
	Networking and participation in relevant events	2
	Industry related events	1
	Local presentations	2
	Informal meetings with local private companies, public authorities, policy makers	20
Meetings and gatherings with policy makers	1	
ZHAW	Presentations at Conferences	1
	Number of entries in local regional national media	6
	Newsletters recipients	200
	Social media followers	400
	Number of publications/papers	1
	Networking and participation in relevant events	2
	Industry related events	1
	Local presentations	2
	Informal meetings with local private companies, public authorities, policy makers	20
Meetings and gatherings with policy makers	1	
TUB	Presentations at Conferences	1
	Number of entries in local regional national media	6
	Newsletters recipients	200
	Social media followers	400
	Number of publications/papers	1
	Networking and participation in relevant events	2
	Industry related events	1
	Local presentations	2
	Informal meetings with local private companies, public authorities, policy makers	20
Meetings and gatherings with policy makers	1	

4.1 Project flyer

The project flyer is an essential tool to raise awareness on the project. Specifically, the leaflet will provide all the necessary information in a concise form regarding the project and its objectives and targets. Printed copies of the brochure (1000 copies) will be distributed among the partners, ensuring that the core information will be widely spread among project partners and stakeholders. The flyer will be a threefold A4 flyer. It will provide the following info: Project logo, logos of project partners and their map location with their websites, a project scope, specific objectives, results and impact. Furthermore, the flyer will provide

contact details of the coordinator including online website of the project and the respective social media identities for Facebook®, Linked-In ® and Twitter®.

4.2 Powerpoint template

A Powerpoint template will be developed for the use by all partners for project- related internal and external presentations.

4.3 INTEND project website

A project website is to be created by Month 2 November 2017, under the responsibility of TUB. It will contain introductory information describing the project, its goals and objectives, details of the consortium partners and a workplan. Furthermore, project deliverables will be posted on the website including two major features of the website based on the projects results: a) the transport research database and the b) updated Transport Synopsis Tool. Details for contacting the consortium members will be made available on the project's website. Thus the website is intended for any interested public party.

More specifically it will have different access levels, downloading function for public deliverables, access to the transport project database and forwarding function to the Transport Synopsis Tool. The INTEND consortium will ensure that the project website and its content is advertised in many platforms including TRIMIS, Eltis and UITP research platforms. The INTEND project website will be accessible at <http://www.intend-project.eu/> and launched by M2 (30.11.2017). As task leader TUB is responsible for the technical development of the website all the other partners are providing support with the concept and contents of the website. Moreover, all partners will proactively deliver contents and material for keeping the website up-to-date. The partners CUE, CERTH and TUB will have administrator rights to change the website content on request of the other partners. The INTEND project website will feature the following functionalities:

- ✓ Overview of project concept, objective, partner description and contacts, consortium, activities, publications and deliverables, news
- ✓ Link to social media (Facebook®, Linked-In ® and Twitter®)
- ✓ Sign-up for project's newsletter
- ✓ Entrance to the data-repository
- ✓ Forwarding function to the Synopsis tool

4.3.1 Web indexing

In order to guarantee that the website is included in the search results of search engines, different actions have to be taken. The three most important search engines are Google (approx. 1.6 billion visitors per month, Bing 400 million visitors per month, Yahoo 300 million visitors per month). [<https://searchenginewatch.com/2016/08/08/what-are-the-top-10-most-popular-search-engines/>]

The main prerequisite for being included in the search results of a search engine is that the site has been indexed by the search engine. In order to continuously update the list of accessible websites, every search engine operator uses so called 'crawlers' that are constantly scanning the internet for new websites.

For that reason, main actions to make search engines aware of new websites are:

- Creating a sitemap on the webpage server that informs the crawler about the website,
- Informing the search engine operator about the website (e.g. for Google this can be done via the webpage developer options included in Gmail accounts),
- Adding the website URL to sections of other topic-related websites,
- Distribution of the URL via social media accounts.

The first two actions are part of the website creation process, the last ones are depending on the successful implementation of the dissemination strategy which includes a constant presence in social media and other dissemination channels.

For the Intend website the first two options are included in the process of creating the website and have thus been already completed. The other activities mentioned, will be intensified with further progress of the project.

4.3.2 Improving Search Ranking

The process of improving the search ranking of websites is known as search engine optimization or search marketing or short SEO (Thomas, 2017).

Although every search engine crawler uses different algorithms to assess and evaluate the importance of a webpage, the main criteria supporting high ranks among other search results can be summarized as follows (Thomas, 2017):

- High quality content,
- Building quality natural backlinks to the website,
- Anchor texts in backlinks,
- On page optimization for search engines,
- Additional search factors
 - Page load speed,
 - Hhttps,
 - Visitor usage

Due to the very short project runtime some of the upper mentioned criteria can only be partly addressed as they are related to a constantly followed marketing strategy.

Nevertheless, the consortium subcontracted a professional company for the website development. The integration of state of the art templates and plug-ins - an in matters of appearance and usability very attractive output - will be reached, that can optimally present the content. Moreover, the project website will contain different presentation formats showing in-depth information (project description, methodology etc.) and advanced easy to handle applications like pop-up windows for brief descriptions (e.g. a slideshow explaining the project in 90sec.). The website will be responsive, meaning to be also readable when using smartphones.

Building high quality natural backlinks to the website is part of the dissemination strategy. By describing the site on the project partner websites, in newsblogs, networking sites and conference sites the creation of backlinks can be realized. Since the consortium already plans to undertake various dissemination actions this criterion is being addressed as well.

The strategy of building anchor text in text links will not be addressed explicitly, as this procedure was used too often and partly abused.

The on-page optimization for search engines is something that will be addressed during site development.

Additional search factors are addressed as well and will be considered during site development. During the project added visible content, especially images, will be checked before upload to guarantee an optimal quality and size (data) balance. The site will use the "https" protocol.

Visitor usage is an indirect factor and can be measured through the click through rate (search query and website hit) and the dwell time (time that visitors spend on the page before coming back to the search engine). Since the ranking algorithms are constantly changing, it is hard to estimate which data is finally being analyzed [https://moz.com/blog/the-2-user-metrics-that-matter-for-seo]. Moreover, being also subject to competition, search engines will not publish the list of data that is being used by them.

However, the last factor (dwell time) can be influenced by the way the content is being presented. For the Intend webpage the long information is only being accessible via subpages and popping up content will require at least one to one a half minutes of time. This will help to keep visitors on the page and thus deliver positive scores.

From the technical point of view there are several website plug-ins existing that help to check and monitor new contents, posts, backlinks to support SEO. The project will also make use of the capabilities of such tools.

5 Dissemination and stakeholders' dialogue

In order to ensure an effective dissemination and stakeholders' dialogue the INTEND project will have three main communication actions comprising:

- ✓ Audio-visual material (project website, Newsletter, Social Media, digital webinar)
- ✓ Publications (Press releases, articles in scientific journal)
- ✓ Event participation / Networking (inter/national conferences, workshops)

Table 2 presents an indicative list of stakeholders that each partner will contact, share results with (newsletters and reports) and invite to the webinars. The stakeholders will also be invited to visit the project's website and social media pages. Furthermore, INTEND will disseminate results to the project's website registered users. Apart from the aforementioned communication channels, INTEND will contact technology websites such as the green car congress (<http://www.greencarcongress.com>) and mobility website like ELTIS (<http://www.eltis.org>) in order to disseminate results to a wider audience. A profile for the INTEND website will also be created on the TRIMIS website thus allowing the research community and other interested parties to see project details and results.

Table 4. Stakeholder network of INTEND partners

Partner	Stakeholder contacts
CUE	Enterprise Europe Network (EEN), European Association of Automotive suppliers (CLEPA), European Business Incubator Network (EBN), FEHRL, ENoLL (Low Carbon Innovations), SEA Europe, UNIFE, Waterborne TP, European Aeronautics Science Network -Technology Innovation Service
CERTH	The Federation of European Private Port Operators and Terminals (FEPORT), The European Sea Ports Organisation (ESPO), European rail Research Network of Excellence (EURNEX), World's Road Transport Organisation (IRU), Transportation Research Board (TRB), ECTRI, HUMANIST, European Technology Platform on logistics-ALICE, European Association of Aviation Training and Educational Organisations (EATEO), Flight Safety Foundation Mediterranean (FSF-MED), EUROCONTROL, International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO)
FTTE	The Community of European Railway and Infrastructure Companies (CER), Enterprise Europe Network, Pro Danube International, Waterways Forward, Transportation Research Board of USA, Stakeholders developed in REACT, METRIC, TRACE projects, South East Europe Transport Observatory (SEETO), Stakeholders from Ministries of transport and numerous transport operators and companies from Balkan countries (Serbia, Montenegro, FYROM, B&H, Croatia, etc)
ZHAW	UIC International Union of Railways, INUAS International Network of Universities of Applied Sciences, SCCER Swiss Competence Centre of Energy Research – section Mobility, ZHAW Centre for Aviation (ZAV), Stakeholders from European Airlines
TUB	EITDigital - "Smart city" stream, Cosmobilities, German transport associations and umbrella organisations, airport operators FRAPORT (Frankfurt Airport) and FBB (Flughafen Berlin-Brandenburg) GmbH

5.1 Newsletters

Three newsletters will be released during the course of the project. The newsletters will aim to summarise and disseminate the project's results to the target groups. The latter consist of the registered users of the INTEND website and the stakeholder groups (section). TUB will provide CERTH/HIT with the list of emails that will be extracted from the INTEND website. CERTH/HIT will be responsible for emailing all the registered users and other contacts with the newsletters. The partners in charge for creating each newsletter issue are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Newsletters and partner allocated

Newsletter	Partner allocation	Due date and month
Newsletter 1: First results from the identification of the future technologies and megatrends	CERTH, FTTE	31/01/2018 - M4
Newsletter 2: Brief results from	TUB, FTTE, CUE	31/03/2018 - M8

future mobility concepts, political imperatives and ANP process		
Newsletter 3: The future transport system and the transport research needs	ZHAW, FTTE	30/09/2018 - M12

5.2 Press releases

The press releases will be spread at local, national and international level according to the dissemination activities, which will take place in the next months. Specifically, the Consortium will publish a total of 2 press releases focusing on specific project issues and milestones and promoting project events. A press release will cover brief results of WP2 and 3 and will be published by CUE through the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN newsletter). A second press release will be published by CERTH in a Greek local newspaper covering brief results of the projects and informing readers about the conclusion of the project and the final conference. In addition the Final conference in Belgrade will receive coverage from Serbian news media (press and TV) which will be organised by the ICTTE's organisers. Information about the conference and INTEND final event will be announced at the Mondo portal (www.mondo.rs) which is one of the most readable portals in the Balkans (second in Serbia). FTTE will make efforts to provide an interview to the media (in Serbian), while a secondary press release of the event will be sent to European research focused websites such as <https://www.euractiv.com/topics/research/>, <http://www.euronews.com/programs/science>, <https://sciencebusiness.net/>. CERTH is responsible for the main press releases while each partner is responsible for the local press releases in each country's media. Regarding local regional national media releases, each consortium member is responsible for producing their own material based on the WP that they are involved in and disseminating to the appropriate media. Examples of such media are: Hellenic Institute of Transportation Engineers¹, Greek supply chain & logistics magazine², The urban mobility observatory website (ELTIS)³, Green Car Congress website⁴, mverkehRen⁵, Logistics Innovation⁶, SchweizLogistik.ch⁷, VCS Magazin⁸, Vision Mobility⁹, Swissfuture¹⁰, Strasse und Verkehr¹¹. Also CUE, a member of the Enterprises Europe Network since its inception, will be responsible for posting articles and press releases at the EEN magazine which reaches more than 2000 subscribers.

5.3 Scientific publications, conferences and other dissemination activities

The INTEND project will produce 4 scientific publications that will be based on the project's main results. Two journal papers will be presented by at the 4th Conference On Sustainable Urban Mobility (CSUM) 24-25th May 2018 at Skiathos, Greece. The two scientific publications

¹ <http://www.ses.gr/index.php/english-about-hite.html>

² <http://www.supply-chain.gr/>

³ <http://www.eltis.org/>

⁴ <http://www.greencarcongress.com/>

⁵ <http://www.umverkehr.ch>

⁶ <http://www.vnl.ch/en-us/services/journal>

⁷ <http://www.schweizlogistik.ch>

⁸ <https://www.verkehrsclub.ch/mitglieder/services/magazin>

⁹ <https://www.vision-mobility.de/de/magazin-und-abonnement>

¹⁰ <https://www.swissfuture.ch/de/magazin-fur-zukunftsmonitoring/>

¹¹ <http://www.vss.ch/zeitschrift-s-v/allgemeines/>

will cover the topics of the future transport technologies from D 2.1 and the identification of the megatrends from D 3.1 respectively. Another three journal papers will be presented at the ICTTE 2018 conference in Belgrade Serbia covering topics such as political imperatives, cutting edge transport technologies and systems and maritime technologies. Table 6 presents the list of papers that will be produced to disseminate INTEND's results into the academic world. Furthermore, as indicated in Table 3 Table 2, the INTEND consortium will participate in various events in order to disseminate the project through various means such as networking with industry, academia and policy makers through meetings, conferences, project presentations or simply handing out project flyers and introducing the project. Table 6 presents the activities that have been planned.

Table 6. INTEND project future publications and dissemination activities

Action No.	Project Month	Description	Location	Partners involved
Main publications				
1	M8	Paper titled: "Mapping of future technologies in the transport sector: an outlook of 2020-2035" will provide results from WP2 –T2.1	Presentation at the 4th CSUM 24-25 th May 2018 at Greece. The paper will also get published in a journal special issue.	CERTH, ZHAW, CUE
2	M8	Paper titled: "Megatrends, A Way To Intentify The Future Transport Challenges"	Presentation at the 4th CSUM 24-25 th May 2018 at Greece. The paper will also get published in a journal special issue.	FTTE, CUE
3	M11	Article about the updated transport synopsis tool	Options: Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering European Journal of Futures Research International Journal of Sustainable Transportation	TUB
4	Accepted by	A paper about the methodologies covered in the	Options: European Journal	All

	maximum M12	INTEND project	of Futures Research	
			FUTURES	
5	Accepted by maximum M12	A paper about relevance for policy and practice (including an overview of future fields of research, research needs and opportunities and guiding principles for policymakers)	Options: Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering European Journal of Futures Research International Journal of Sustainable Transportation TRB	ZHAW
6	M12	Article regarding the findings related to political imperatives	Presentation at the ICTTE Belgrade 2018 (27.-28. September 2018)	TUB
7	M12	A paper with special focus on cutting-edge transport technologies and transport systems transformation	Presentation at the ICTTE Belgrade 2018 (27.-28. September 2018)	ZHAW
9	M12	A paper with special on the Maritime technologies and specifically ports and energy managent	Presentation at the ICTTE Belgrade 2018 (27.-28. September 2018)	CERTH
Secondary dissemination activities				
10	M2	Presentation of project (Invited presentation of the project objectives, methodologies and expected results to the audience composed of the EC, ministries, industry and academia representatives from the Danubean countries) - done	4th Conference on Transport and Research in the Danube region, 6th-7th November, 2017, Ljubljana, Slovenia	FTTE
11	M3	Presentation and networking	XXXV Symposium on novel postal and telecommunication	FTTE

D5.1 Dissemination and exploitation strategy plan

			technologies, 05-06th December, 2017, Belgrade, Serbia ¹²	
12	M4	Leaflets and Networking	97th Transport Research Board Annual Meeting, January 7-11, 2018, Washington, D.C	CERTH
13	M4	Leaflets and networking, including a meeting with a corporate strategist of the Swiss Federal Railways	Energie Apéros Aarau 18./23./25. January 2018	ZHAW
14	M4	Presentation, leaflets and networking	Midlands Intelligent Mobility Conference 2018, 24.01.2018, Nottingham	CUE
15	M5	Leaflets and networking	16 th Conference of The Hellenic Company of Operational Research 15-17 February, Piraeus, Greece ¹³	CERTH
16	M6	Presentation & leaflets	6th International Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship ICIE 2018, 5 - 6 March 2018, Washington DC, USA	CUE
17	M6	Leaflets and networking	XXIV Conference YU INFO, 11-14th March, 2018, Kopaonik, Serbia ¹⁴	FTTE
18	M7	Leaflets and networking	5th International	CERTH

¹² <http://postel.sf.bg.ac.rs/> - in Serbian; This conference was organized by FTTE. Among many postal and telecommunication topics, it also covered numerous transportation research issues in the segment of intelligent transportation systems

¹³ <http://mcda2018.puas.gr/>. The conference thematic area is about sea shipping and transport. The conference site is in Greek.

¹⁴ This conference is focused on ICT, but regularly covers transport related issues, so transport researchers always take part and present their findings. FTTE will use this opportunity to disseminate the project itself and project results among the transport researchers who will be participating at the 2018 edition of the conference

D5.1 Dissemination and exploitation strategy plan

			Conference on Control, Decision and Information Technologies (CoDiT), April 10-13 2018 Special session Optimisation in Electric Vehicle Fleet Operations, Thessaloniki Greece	
19	M7	Leaflets and networking	Transport Research Arena 2018, 16-19.04.2018, Vienna	CUE, ZHAW
20	M8	Presentation, leaflets and networking	2 nd Conference, "Transport for Today's Society", Bitola, FYROM, 17-19 th May, 2018	FTTE
21	M9	Article regarding dissemination of the project and brief results of future technologies, mobility concepts etc (in Greek)	Magazine of the Hellenic Institute of Transportation Engineers, June issue 2018	CERTH
22	M9	Presentation, leaflets and networking	International Conference On Transport Science, 14-15 th June, 2018, Portorož, Slovenia	FTTE
23	M9	Leaflets and networking	ISPIM Innovation Conference, 17-20 June 2018, Stockholm	ZHAW
24	M12	Presentation, leaflets and networking	Behave 2018 5th European Conference on Behaviour and Energy Efficiency, 5-7 September 2018, Zürich, Switzerland	ZHAW
25	M12	Presentation, leaflets and	SYMOPIS 2018:	FTTE

		networking	XLV Symposium on Operational Research, 22-28th September, 2018, venue – TBD, Serbia ¹⁵	
26	M12	Presentation, leaflets and networking	The 21st EURO Working Group on Transportation Meeting, EWGT 2018, 17-19 September 2018, Braunschweig, Germany	FTTE
27	M12	Final conference/ additional networking	ICTTE Belgrade 2018 (27.-28. September 2018)	All

5.4 Digital webinar

Considering the importance of the ANP model evaluation, a digital webinar will be organized by FTTE in order to gain the evaluation efficiency. Thus, the whole event will consist of two stages – the explanatory stage and the ANP model evaluation stage. In the explanatory stage, the webinar platform will be used to prepare participants for taking part in the evaluation process. The webinar is expected to be like a short movie that gives instructions about how to answer the survey. It will be conducted by the moderator, who will present the goals, which should be reached by ANP model evaluation, as well as some important steps that should help participants to better understand the survey process. The webinar platform is based on Java and Adobe Flash; it will have fully interactive capabilities for all users (controllable by moderator/administrator), highly tunable audio/video streaming and document/presentation sharing capability.

The ANP model evaluation stage is the second stage of the digital webinar. It will be organized in a form of survey and driven by the Custom Multiservice Platform (CMSP¹⁶). CMPS will proactively monitor the consistence of participants' responses. In case of inconsistent response, ANP intelligence engine will suggest such a response is more consistent to the corresponding relations. CMSP is custom coded fully interactive survey that is consisted of the PHP¹⁷ based survey frontend, MySQL¹⁸ custom database, as well as

¹⁵ No online link yet. This conference has been taken place for around 50 years and it is well known among the researchers in the Balkans. The conference is about operational researches, but several sessions are regularly devoted to the transport researches. On-line link will be established soon

¹⁶ Custom Multiservice Platform (CMSP) is custom coded fully interactive survey, developed by FTTE

¹⁷ PHP, which stands for "PHP: Hypertext Pre-processor" is a widely-used Open Source general-purpose scripting language that is especially suited for development of interactive web pages.

¹⁸ MySQL stands for a widely-used Open Source relational database management system. It is designed for the purpose of programming and managing data stored in databases, by using Structured Query Language (SQL).

Python¹⁹ based evaluation engine with ANP²⁰ intelligence. Digital webinar and CSMP engines will be designed in a way to fully protect participant's privacy.

During ANP model evaluation stage, webinar channel will be opened for verbal and chat consulting purposes. The webinar will take place in project month 7 (April 2018).

5.5 Wikipedia

An INTEND Wikipedia page will be created with a brief project description and a link to the website.

5.6 Social media

5.6.1 Facebook®

Facebook is a popular free social networking website that allows registered users to create profiles, upload photos and video, send messages and keep in touch with friends, family and colleagues. The site, which is available in 37 different languages, includes public features such as:

- ❖ Marketplace - allows members to post, read and respond to classified ads.
- ❖ Groups - allows members who have common interests to find each other and interact.
- ❖ Events - allows members to publicize an event, invite guests and track who plans to attend.
- ❖ Pages - allows members to create and promote a public page built around a specific topic.
- ❖ Presence technology - allows members to see which contacts are online and chat.

The INTEND Facebook® account “intendeuropeanproject” (<https://www.facebook.com/IntendEuropeanProject/>) (created by CERTH/HIT) allows a quick overview regarding project details and updates, provides news from other relevant projects and material from project meetings (photos, presentations etc.). The account was created on 12th November 2017.

5.6.2 Linked-IN®

LinkedIn® is a professional network and discussions are rather fact based. The LinkedIn account “INTEND (INtendify future Transport rEsearch NeedS) European Project”, created on 12th November 2017, will be used to engage with a professional public in discussions and to disseminate project results. The following content will be published on the LinkedIn community established by CERTH/HIT:

- ✓ News on the project, e.g. news from the INTEND network, project developments or project meetings etc.
- ✓ News from others, e.g. related projects or project partners etc.

¹⁹ Python is a high-level programming language for general-purpose programming. It supports multiple programming paradigms, including object-oriented, imperative, functional and procedural.

²⁰ The analytic network process (ANP) is a more general form of the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) used in multi-criteria decision analysis.

Content of the discussion forum will be managed by CERTH/HIT. Partners are encouraged to:

- Provide input regarding news that should be promoted
- Link and interact: Partners can launch discussions and write their own contributions via their personal profiles.

5.6.3 Twitter®

Twitter® is a very effective tool to spread important pieces of information within seconds to a broad public. Therefore short messages (140 characters maximum) can be published to inform about the latest project news.

The INTEND Twitter® account “INTEND_Project” (https://twitter.com/intend_project) (created by CERTH/HIT) allows a quick overview of what is going on in the project, providing links to related websites for more details plus giving the opportunity to comment on information. By generating followers, an INTEND community will be developed, sharing the news in time and keeping in touch if desired. The account was created on 13th November 2017.

General advice for Tweets:

- Tweets should be kept between 100 and 120 characters
- Proper sentences should be written
- The use of pictures encourages retweets
- Conversations should be encouraging (by posing questions, thanking others that mentioned the project etc.)
- 1/3 of the tweets should be about the project, 1/3 should be about sharing content, 1/3 should be interactions with others
- Tweets from others should be shared (e.g. similar projects etc.): This creates co-references
- Shortened weblinks should be inserted

Hashtags (#) are used to reach specific target groups and identify key concepts. They should be as specific as possible. A maximum of two hashtags per tweet is recommended. The following hashtags could be used in relation to INTEND– always depending on the content of the tweet, e.g.:

#INTEND_project #H2020 #futuretransport #megatrends, #FutureofEurope, #EUTransportResearch

5.6.4 YouTube®

A short video explaining the INTEND project concept, its aims and objectives and expected outcomes. YouTube will be used as the platform where the video will be posted and it will be communicated across INTEND’s Social media accounts as well as the rest of the partners. The INTEND video will be also visible on the project’s homepage. The content will be created by CERTH while the creation of the video will be outsourced to a video creator. To be created at M6.

5.6.5 Social media updates strategy

Table 7 presents INTEND's frequency of reporting on the social media. Specifically, the table shows the type of actions that will need to be reported in order to make the public aware of these activities i.e. the publication of deliverables. The schedule column presents the project month and number of occurrences of the project action i.e. at M5 2 deliverables at expected to be released which will be posted in the news section of the website, FB, Twitter and LinkedIn. The updates will cover all social media accounts. When partners attend conferences or events where the INTEND project is promoted/disseminated, they will have to make relevant posts on the project's social media platforms. This can be done through their personal accounts and sharing it to project's homepage for each account or sending the appropriate information to CERTH/HIT who administers the accounts. In each case the procedure stated in section 5.8 must be followed.

Table 7. Social media reporting of INTEND activities

Project action	Website news section	Social media platform			Partner responsible	Schedule
		Facebook	Twitter	LinkedIn		
Release of public deliverables	X	X	X	X	CERTH/HIT	M5 (2), M7 (2), M8, M10 (2), M12
Project meeting	X	X	X	X	CERTH/HIT	M4, M9
Participation in conferences or events	X	X	X	X	All	M3, M4(2), M5, M6 (2), M7 (2), M8 (2), M9 (4), M12 (3)
Project website creation alert	X	X	X	X	CERTH/HIT	M2
Newsletter	X	X	X	X	CERTH/HIT	M4, M8, M12
Flyer	X	X	X	X	CERTH/HIT	M2

Table 8 presents the frequency of non-project related posting on social media, i.e. links to interesting other projects' results, interesting news articles, reports or studies related to transport and INTEND. The posts will be made by CERTH/HIT while all partners will contribute.

Table 8. Frequency of non project related postings on social media

Number of postings	Social media platform			Frequency
	Facebook	Twitter	LinkedIn	
	1	2	1	Per week

5.7 Project meetings

Table 9 presents the relevant project meetings that will be carried out in the project's duration.

Table 9. Project meetings for INTEND project

Meeting Number	Date & Location	Partner responsible
1	24-25 th January 2018 Berlin, Germany	TUB
2	21-22 nd June 2018 Thessaloniki, Greece	CERTH/HIT

5.8 Final conference

At the end of the project the consortium will organize a final conference to present the project's results to EU officials and other transport industry stakeholders. In this conference the consortium expects the participation of 50 + transport industry stakeholders and EU officials. The final project conference will take place in Belgrade during the ICTTE conference on 27th and 28th September 2018. The conference will be hosted at the Hotel Moscow, where a room will be allocated for half a day or more to deliver the project final results to the audience. This will run as one of the parallel sessions of the ICTTE conference. The INTEND session will be used in two ways: a) Present the project findings and b) present consortium papers with project results that will be sent to the ICTTE conference. In addition conference papers from other researchers covering relevant topics to those covered by INTEND will be presented in the parallel session. Plans for a small number of guest speakers from the transport industry are also envisaged. A reality check will take place prior to the final conference in June at Brussels where a small representation of the INTEND consortium will present project results to the P.O. and Brussels officials.

5.9 Project synergies

INTEND aims to establish synergies with relevant projects in order to strengthen both dissemination and exploitation potential of the project. Synergies will be established with the following projects:

MOBILITY4EU (CERTH: Partner): The project will deliver a vision for the European transport system in 2030 and an Action plan including a roadmap to implement that vision. The construction of the future scenario and technologies identification is heavily based on stakeholder participation. Recommendations for tangible measures in research, innovation and implementation will be derived.

The INTEND project will disseminate results by networking with the MOBILITY4EU project led by CERTH. Initial contacts have been made with the projects coordinator VDI/VDE Innovation + Technology GmbH in order to receive a special invitation to the project's stakeholder group. Contacts that will be established during the MOBILITY4EU event will be used as additional contacts and will be invited. INTEND will participate in an upcoming M4EU workshop in March where it will provide expert feedback to M4EU's research and will also inform the participants about the INTEND's upcoming results. In addition, the M4EU consortium has been invited to participate in the ICTTE Belgrade conference.

NEWBITS H2020– New business models for C-ITS (CUE: Partner): The project delivers innovative business models for the efficient exploitation and application of C-ITS solutions. INTEND will exchange experience in the terms of future directions in the ITS arena. Also NEWBITS will participate in the final conference of INTEND and provide access to their network of experts that could potentially participate in the INTENS surveys

NOESIS H2020- Big Data in Transport (CUE, FTTE: Partner): NOESIS will create a Decision Support tool (i.e., methodology) which will be able to predict the value generated (i.e., socioeconomic impact) from Big Data technologies. INTEND will obtain insights on the Big Data potential in shaping the future of transportation while we will also share results on Megatrends (WP3) which will help NOESIS structure their use cases around the key challenges of the future.

INNOTRANS INTERREG- Enhancing transport innovation (CUE: Leader): INNOTRANS aims to boost the innovation capacities of the regions in the field of transport. INNOTRANS employs a rich data base of policy makers that have an interest in supporting transport innovation. This can be utilised by INTEND in conducting the surveys- capturing the policy makers views on key future challenges faced in the various regions. Also INTEND can offer an evaluation of megatrends and challenges (WP3) but also policy recommendations (WP4) that can be – to a varied degree- applicable for the INNOTRANS regions.

SCCER Mobility (ZHAW: Partner): The Swiss Competence Center for Energy Research – Efficient Technologies and Systems for Mobility (SCCER Mobility) aims at developing knowledge and technologies which support a transition from the current transport system to a more sustainable one (supporting minimal CO2 output, primary energy demand and virtually zero-pollutant emissions). In its initial phase, the primary focus lied on developing and testing new technological concepts. In the current second phase of the project, this knowledge will be transferred to other sectors through cross-capacity projects as well as interactions with

different stakeholder groups. In this context, dissemination of the results of the INTEND project could turn out to be a valuable input for the further steps in this project.

CITIES MULTIMODAL INTERREG B – Baltic Sea Region Programme (TUB (ZTG): Partner). The project focuses on dense inner-city areas with growing population and mixed use offering good opportunities for sustainable mobility. They can be forerunner for other city quarters and cities in the BSR, but their attractiveness reaches its limit because of too many cars – a good starting point to switch from car oriented traffic planning to mobility management.

The experts/ planners coming from the 10 cities involved can help to identify transport research needs on the side of municipal stakeholders.

5.10 Reporting and Monitoring of dissemination activities

A monitoring and reporting procedure has been established in order to ensure that the measurable dissemination indicators are met as set in Table 2, Table 3, Table 7 and Table 8. Specifically, all partners will be asked to report to CERTH/HIT their dissemination activities on a monthly basis. Participation in conferences should be reported as soon as possible in order to be uploaded soon after to the news section of the website. An internal monitoring template has been created and will be updated by CERTH/HIT with each partner’s reporting figures. A sample of the templates are provided in Annex 1

A reporting template for dissemination events has been created in order for each partner to provide some information when the INTEND project is disseminated to the public. The main idea behind the template is that whenever a partner attends an event where the INTEND project has been mentioned/covered to a brief extent, they will have to fill out the following form. The form has two roles: 1) Report on the dissemination events of the project. The form will be used to collect some basic information about where the INTEND project has been disseminated in order to upload relevant information to Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. 2) The reporting template will also collect information that can be used as feedback for the newsletters.

Table 10. Dissemination events reporting template

Partner involved	i.e. any of the INTEND partners
Location	i.e. Skiathos, Greece
Date	i.e. 23/05/2018
Event name	i.e. 4th CSUM
Event type	i.e. conference, meeting with transport stakeholders, meeting with EU officials, project
Event scope and brief description	i.e. Conference on urban mobility, presentation of the project to local transport stakeholders, presentation of results to EU officials
Event website	i.e. http://csum.civ.uth.gr/
Role of the partners	i.e. project presentation or attendee etc,
Brief description of the partners’ role in the event	i.e. The partner presented their paper titled “....” regarding results from WPX . Networking with attendees took place and people were informed about the project. Flyers were distributed
Pictures to be attached as files to the email	Number of pictures

6 Open Access

The dissemination approach of the INTEND project complies with the “Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020”, published by the European Commission and the article 29.2 of the Model Grant Agreement for H2020 projects, thus ensuring open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

By this, results of publicly funded research can be disseminated more broadly and faster, to the benefit of researchers, innovative industry and citizens. Open access can further boost the visibility of European research, and in particular offer small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) access to the latest research for utilization.

For peer-reviewed scientific publications resulting from the INTEND project, open access (OA) will be guaranteed by measures of the “green” or “gold” model, defined by the European Commission in the following way:

- ✓ **Self-archiving / Green open access:** implies that the peer-reviewed and accepted manuscript is archived by the author – or a representative – in machine-readable format in an online repository. The depositor must make sure that the open access to the publication is given within 6 months after deposit. INTEND will utilize the OpenAIRE platform, which gives access to numerous online archives in different research domains (www.openaire.eu), to deposit manuscripts for “green open access” in the most impact-oriented manner.
- ✓ **Open publishing / Gold open access:** implies that an article is immediately provided in open access mode as published. It requests that also the deposit of a machine-readable electronic copy of the latest published version of the peer-reviewed and accepted manuscript in a repository in order to ensure long-term preservation of the article.

The following guidelines apply for the INTEND project:

- ✓ **Non-confidential data** / information / outcomes will be open access on the project website.
- ✓ **Confidential data** such as internal workshops, project memoranda etc. will be shared and verified by all partners to be used in non-confidential data / information / outcome.
- ✓ A number of **best practices and guidelines** for working with Open Data, promoted by organisations such as the Open Data Foundation (www.opendatafoundation.org) or Open Knowledge Foundation (www.okfn.org) will be carefully considered in order to ensure the biggest impact of the project data.
- ✓ Most of the **publications** related to the result of the project will be “gold” open access to be available for all people on the project website and other possible websites. Manuscripts will be deposited in an institutional and / or subject-based and / or centralised repository of the choice of the author(s).
- ✓ Journal papers stemming from the results of the INTEND project will be made available through open access journals and will be available through sources such as sciencedirect.com

- ✓ Conference presentations of results from the INTEND project will be made available at the project's available but also through the conference's site and proceedings.
- ✓ All public deliverables of the project will be made available at the website <https://intend-project.eu/> under the publications section.

7 Exploitation

INTEND will be putting special emphasis on the exploitation of the results. Fundamentally, there are three groups of key project outputs which will be used after the lifetime of the project:

- a) Transport projects database: The repository will accessible via the INTEND website to provide a comprehensive picture of all forward looking studies focusing on technological developments, megatrends and policies. In addition the Transport projects & future technologies synopses handbook will summarize the results of various transport projects briefly and in a comprehensive way. This will be made available in hard copy and electronic format and it will be presented to the EU officials in the project's final conference meeting. This handbook will remain one of the key components for exploitation of key project results.
- b) The Research Agenda: The agenda will identify research needs, priorities and opportunities coming along with the transforming transport system. As new technologies and mobility concepts spread by interacting with individual mobility behaviour the role of end users in shaping the market and the mobility paradigms will also be considered, so to achieve a more holistic outcome. This new research agenda should not just address identified problems and gaps, but mainly show promising fields contributing to general social and economic development.
- c) The updated Transport Synopsis tool: To enable a wide range of stakeholders to gain access to some of the results, INTEND will develop an online platform, the INTEND Transport Synopsis tool that will constitute a dynamic knowledge base repository on the major developments in the transport sector. This will provide a visualisation of the INTEND's main outcomes from WP3 and WP2 (technology trends, megatrends, political imperatives). The basis for the platform will be Transport Synopsis Tool which is already developed under the project RACE2050 coordinated by TUB.

Lastly, the project website will be maintained for 4 years after the end of the project while the update Synopsis tool will be hosted permanently by TUB.

7.1 Exploitation of the results by the partners

The following section explains the way that each partner will exploit the project results based on their expertise, organisation's characteristics and networks.

Table 11. Exploitation plan of the results

Partner	Exploitation plan
CUE	<p>The business model of CUE stands on three pillars: education, research, and collaboration. INTEND maintains an active programme of industrial as well as traditional and interdisciplinary academic collaboration that spans student-based projects, networking activities, and funded research projects. Since the support of research is at the core of CUE's mission, CUE collaborates with other research and business communities when there is a mutual interest and potential for synergy.</p> <p>CUE runs a number of initiatives that focus on Knowledge and Technology Transfer such as the Enterprise Europe Network. The network provides a very good pull of experts on a pan-European base that can be utilised in INTEND but also provides a very good opportunity for using the INTEND results for actual transport companies, intermediaries and policy makers in the future.</p> <p>The main exploitation strategy is to offer to policy makers and companies that are already cooperating with CUE on many levels (commercial, non commercial, research based, etc) extra knowledge in the field of future directions for transport and assist them to take more informed decisions based on the state-of-the-art situation but also based on the predictions about future developments. In order to achieve this, CUE maintains contact with the main stakeholders in transport, to give them opportunities to review the INTEND findings and get their input on needs and points of view on the research and technology important issues.</p> <p>CUE organises a policy briefing meetings with the local policy makers every 6 months (Coventry City Council, Birmingham City Council, Stratford upon Avon City Council) Their transport department heads participate in these meetings where CUE presents them a synopsis on the main developments in their transport projects including INTEND. As one of their goals is to also further improve the Regional Operational Programme (ERDF), they are very interested in obtaining more information on promising transport research fields so they can incorporate them in the regional funding plan</p>
CERTH/HIT	<p>CERTH/HIT will exploit the results of the project through national stakeholder channels. The national stakeholders will have the ability to focus on domestic research efforts in the transport sector in fields that are more applicable to the priorities set by the Greek government and adjusting these priorities accordingly based on the indicated future research agenda and technologies. The fact that the INTEND project brings in a plethora of results under one roof, especially in terms of technologies, can help the Greek transport stakeholders to focus the funding on the domestic research to certain under-developed areas, which require attention and could enable the country to harmonise its targets with the rest of the EU.</p> <p>Furthermore, CERTH/HIT aims to exploit the project's results via a</p>

	<p>MOBILITY4EU project outreach event.</p> <p>Part of CERTH/HIT's staff are also lecturers in various universities in Greece, teaching transport engineering in undergraduate and postgraduate level. Part of the results will be integrated into the syllabi of the lectures.</p>
<p>FTTE</p>	<p>FTTE is specialized in research in all fields and areas of the traffic and transport sector. The Faculty is active in the area of facilitating transport policy-making and strategic development decisions, through the participation in related projects and studies, providing opinions, etc. In that context, FTTE envisions INTEND as a very important platform for identifying transport research needs in Europe, which will build on our research expertise and improve our teaching processes and networking capabilities.</p> <p>FTTE will exploit the results of INTEND to increase its research potentials and understanding of megatrends affecting both freight and passenger transportation and which are most likely to impact the transport concepts of the future. Therefore, FTTE will explore options to publish research findings, achieved by participating in the INTEND project, in scientific journals, conferences and workshops, as the most typical places to disseminate the knowledge to global research community.</p> <p>The knowledge gained from the INTEND project as well as project results and recommendations will be used to enhance lecture materials for both undergraduate and postgraduate courses. We will also use the findings on implications of the key megatrends for future transport concepts and other project results, to identify new research challenges in this research field, and therefore to facilitate on-going and future MSc and PhD projects.</p> <p>Cooperation with INTEND project partners, as well as other universities, companies and institutions will enable synergies especially in complementary scientific areas. Therefore, INTEND results and established cooperation will be used as inputs to future research projects and common research and educational activities.</p> <p>Based on INTEND's recommendations and conclusions, FTTE will investigate options to offer its support to foster the evolution of transport research agendas in Serbia and, if possible, other countries of the Western Balkan area and Danube region.</p>
<p>ZHAW</p>	<p>Due to ZHAW's link to the Swiss transport sector, the main focus in our national exploitation activities will lie on spreading the results of the INTEND project to various relevant stakeholder-groups on a national, regional and local scale. Through this, we aim to raise greater awareness and interest for future research needs and priorities and make a valuable contribution for developing the scientific landscape in Switzerland towards more innovation in the future. On an international level results will be communicated in and used for talks, expert and consultancy activities as well as for scientific and public publications.</p> <p>In concrete terms, our activities will comprise information, recommendations</p>

	<p>and guidance of political authorities and stakeholders from the industry in the course of project work, during conferences and in informal exchanges. A mobility-laboratory, which is currently in the design process, with the aim of communicating future challenges of the transport sector to policymakers as well as to partners in the industry and students, will be used for integrating the knowledge resulting from the INTEND project. To increase the impact on a scientific level, knowledge transfer will be cross-linked to other research institutes. The examined blind spots and research needs will be considered in the daily research activities and communicated externally to fill the research gaps by promoting future research projects in the relevant fields.</p>
<p>TUB</p>	<p>TUB aims at continuing to follow the path opened-up by initiating the RACE 2050 project. The epistemological motivation of TUB to participate in INTEND is to deepen the knowledge on how political imperatives are being generated and how, when and by whom they are being added to political agendas.</p> <p>Being in contact with and advisor to national, regional and local transport planning stakeholders, TUB will be able to forward the cognitions gained by this project. This will affect their perception of future trends and technologies and will help them to re-align the transport system's development path in a way that it better serves the future societal needs and coming from the European perspective sensitizes them to also consider aspects of the further European integration. The adoption of innovative ideas produced by INTEND will also have the potential to affect national research agendas and the formulated needs in terms of technology towards the transport industry hence supporting the competitiveness of the German and European transport industry.</p> <p>The knowledge and cognitions generated by INTEND will also find entrance into the lectures at TU Berlin. Especially the post-graduate students of the new master program "Sustainable Mobility Management" at TUB will benefit from this.</p>

7.2 Exploitation of the results by the academia

The project results may be used by academics and researchers, exploring the issue of new technologies, megatrends and their effect on future mobility concepts, and political imperatives required to enable these new technologies becoming mainstream. Academics may find a synopsis of a broad range of technologies under one roof, thus compiling knowledge across all transport mode sectors. This could assist in identifying both past and present projects that have researched specific technologies and their results. Thus, it may allow researchers to identify potential areas that are under-researched, or technologies that are promising yet require further development. In the same manner the project deliverables and website will be a useful resource for finding references. The main way of exploitation will be mostly revealed after the project results will be published and the significance to the academic community understood through the final conference. Project outcomes maybe

used as teaching material in undergraduate and postgraduate courses and as a basis in MSc and PhD theses and dissertations.

7.3 Exploitation of the results by the European officials

The European Commission remains the main target group of INTEND’s project results as also discussed during the INTEND’s Kick of meeting with the Project Officer. The main feedback for the officials will be the megatrends and future mobility concepts from the forward-looking projects and future technologies from various research projects across the transport modes. The aforementioned results as well as the research agenda of WP4 will be exploited by the EU officials as input for the elaboration of a transport research agenda in the medium term, with long term impact on the competitiveness of the European Transport sector and on the achievement of EU policy goals. In this regard, a workshop will be held in Brussels with EC officials in June 2018. The exploitation of the results will help prepare the research priorities and needs for the upcoming FP9.

7.4 SWOT analysis of project exploitation potential

The following section consists of the SWOT (Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis that has been carried out to identify key success factors and key barriers of the project’s key outcomes.

Table 12. SWOT analysis of the exploitation strategy

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Strong background from coordination and participation in key relevant projects -Broad coverage of transport sector -Well established contacts with several transport associations and stakeholders -Marketable design of the key project outcomes which increases the likelihood of them serving as key reference in the sector -Introduction of the project results to academic syllabi for young engineers and researchers -Sound research methodology that incorporates the views of a large pull of experts minimizing subjective conclusions - Collaboration with other projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Limited project duration -Relevant research outcomes mainly from H2020 are not yet available -Short term outlook of the project (2035) -Wild cards are not considered
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Network of affiliated stakeholder groups -Broad already established dissemination activities at 22 scheduled events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Technology changes rapidly -Adaptation of project results to the industry needs

<p>-Participation of INTEND partners in other relevant ongoing projects</p> <p>-Promotional and awareness raising event with the context of a major traffic and transport engineering conference (ICTTE 2018, Belgrade) reaching a broad audience</p>	<p>-Wild cards scenarios might be implemented (and therefore the direction of the megatrends might completely change)</p>
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8 Information on EU funding and use of the EU emblem / Exclusion of Commission responsibility (description)

As described in the Grant Agreement, for any publication and dissemination of results stemming from INTEND – both in printed or electronic form – the EU emblem and the following sentence are obligatory:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769638.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

The EU emblem can be downloaded via the following link: http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/index_en.htm .

Only in cases where the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, this rule does not apply. Furthermore, any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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Annex 1

Figure 4 below presents a sample of the internal template that has been created in order for CERTH/HIT to monitor for compliance against targets, the dissemination activities that are reported by the partners. The dissemination reporting template contains a table for each partner.

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	Total	Target
	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September		
CUE														
Presentations at Conferences													0	1
Number of entries in local regional national media													0	6
Newsletters recipients													0	200
Social media followers													0	400
Number of publications/papers													0	1
Number of press releases (produced by CERTH, distributed to media by the partner)													0	1
Networking and participation in relevant events													0	2
Industry related events													0	1
Local presentations													0	2
Informal meetings with local private companies, public authorities, policy makers													0	20
Meetings and gatherings with policy makers													0	1

Figure 4. Internal dissemination reporting template

Figure 5 presents a sample of the monitoring template for ensuring that the dissemination targets for social media are met. The N/C abbreviation stands for not completed.

	January M4						Frequency	Target
	Week 1	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday		
Non project related Twitter		N/C				N/C	0	2
Non project related FB			N/C				0	1
Non project related LinkedIn			N/C				0	1
							0	
	Week 2	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Frequency	Target
Non project related Twitter		N/C				N/C	0	2
Non project related FB			N/C				0	1
Non project related LinkedIn			N/C				0	1
							0	
	Week 3	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Frequency	Target
Non project related Twitter		N/C				N/C	0	2
Non project related FB			N/C				0	1
Non project related LinkedIn			N/C				0	1
							0	
	Week 4	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Frequency	Target
Non project related Twitter		N/C				N/C	0	2
Non project related FB			N/C				0	1
Non project related LinkedIn			N/C				0	1
Project meeting on FB				N/C	N/C		0	1
Project meeting on Twitter				N/C	N/C		0	1
Project meeting on LinkedIn				N/C	N/C		0	1
Project meeting on news section				N/C	N/C		0	1
Newsletter on FB						N/C	0	1
Newsletter on Twitter						N/C	0	1
Newsletter on LinkedIn						N/C	0	1
Newsletter on news section						N/C	0	1

Figure 5. Sample of the internal monitoring template for dissemination activities